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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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P-16: THE EXPRESSION OF VIRULENCE GENES IN *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* AFTER CONTACT WITH HCQDS/PDMS

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Staphylococcus aureus is one of the most common opportunistic bacteria infecting human and causing skin infections, it is widely distributed and have a high survival rate in dry environments, e.g. on surfaces of inanimate objects. Virulence in *S. aureus* is largely under the regulation of two loci, *sarA* and *agr*.

Hydrophobic carbon quantum dots (hCQDs) are well-known for their antibacterial properties. They are activated by blue LEDs to produce singlet oxygen which exert potent antibacterial activity. Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) is used in various biomedical applications including catheters, bandages and medical implants as they are biocompatible and chemically stable. In order to add extra value – antimicrobial - for this polymer, hCQDs were incorporated in it. In this study we analyzed gene expression of 4 virulent genes (*agrA*, *psma*, *rsp* and *rsaC*) in response to contact with PDMS doped with hCQDs.

hCQDs were prepared according to procedure described by Stankovic et al.¹. The hCQDs/PDMS nanocomposites were prepared by dipping of PDMS samples in hCQDs solution in toluene. The hCQDs/PDMS nanocomposites were dried at 80 °C for 12 h to get rid of toluene.

Bacterial suspension of *S. aureus* (3.1×10^6 CFU/mL) was inoculated on the surface of PDMS/hCQDs samples and exposed to blue light for 5, 10 and 15 minutes. The samples were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Bacteria were recovered and total RNA isolation, cDNA generation, and real-time quantitative reverse transcription-PCR was performed on the recovered bacteria. The genes analyzed were *agrA*, *psma*, *rsp* and *rsaC*.

All four genes were downregulated in a time-dependent manner. The highest downregulation of gene expression occurred after 15 min of blue light exposure in *psma* and *rsp*, respectively. These genes are responsible for lytic activity against mammalian cells and triggering cutaneous inflammation and their downregulation would decrease the virulence of the bacteria.

1. Stankovic, N. K., et al. "Antibacterial and antibiofouling properties of light triggered fluorescent hydrophobic carbon quantum dots Langmuir–Blodgett thin films." *ACS Sus Chem Eng* 6.3 (2018): 4154-4163.

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